

Genetic architecture of behavioural resilience to ocean acidification

Robert Lehmann, Celia Schunter, Megan J. Welch, Stefan T. Arold, Göran E. Nilsson, Jesper N. Tegner, Philip L. Munday, and Timothy Ravasi

Supplementary Information

S1 Fig. After establishing behavioural phenotypes, adults were separated into breeding pairs of behaviourally tolerant or sensitive individuals. The resulting offspring were reared under four different CO₂ conditions for two durations, until the age of 5 weeks and 5 months: a) kept at Control CO₂ conditions (Control); b) kept at Control conditions for five weeks/months and acutely exposed to elevated CO₂ for four days before euthanasia (Acute); c) exposure directly at hatching to elevated CO₂ during the entire development (Developmental) and d) exposed directly after hatching to elevated CO₂ but parents were also previously kept at elevated CO₂ conditions (Transgenerational). All fish subjected to these treatments were offspring of five parental pairs each with tolerant and sensitive phenotypes, respectively.

S2 Fig. Hi-C clustering capturing physical contact probability of genome assembly scaffolds.

S3 Fig. Whole genome alignment of Illumina short-read based *A. polyacanthus* reference genome GCA_002109545.1 vs. PacBio long-read based *A. polyacanthus* assembly.

S4 Fig. Comparison of transposable element landscapes of the *A. polyacanthus* reference genome assemblies based on **a)** PacBio long reads **b)** Illumina short reads GCA_002109545.1. The Kimura substitution level on the x-axis suggests the age of the annotated Transposable Element families.

S5 Fig. a) Structural annotation of the mitochondrial genome assembly. **b)** Phylogeny derived of mitochondrial and nuclear marker genes of various Pomacentridae species. The *A. polyacanthus* genome assembly presented here and the prior version GCA_002109545.1 are referred to as Long-read based and Short-read based, respectively. The concatenated DNA sequences of ATP synthase 8 and 6 genes, cytochrome b, and RAG1 were aligned with ClustalW and a phylogenetic tree was constructed with raxml.

S6 Fig. Principal component analysis of pruned genome-wide single nucleotide polymorphism set of all re-sequenced individuals. Parental individuals of the F₀ generation are shown in red, their offspring individuals (F₁ generation) are shown in gray. Behavioral phenotypes of the parents are represented as triangle (tolerant) and circle (sensitive).

S7 Fig. Genetic differentiation measure distributions across all SNPs. Genome-wide distribution of a) XP-nSL values for all SNPs together with a b) quantile-quantile plot. c) XP-nSL distributions per chromosome. The employed cutoffs defining critical SNPs are shown as grey dashed lines. Similar d) genome-wide distribution, e) quantile-quantile plots, and f) per-chromosome distributions for XP-EHH. The distribution of F_{st} values is shown in g).

S8 Fig. Genetic differentiation measure distributions across all genomic windows of a) XP-nSL, b) XP-EHH, and c) F_{st} . The cutoffs selecting the top 0.2% of windows are shown as grey dashed lines.

S9 Fig. Molecular effect of SNP mutation Met348Thr. AlphaFold model of cadherin repeats 3 and 4 (CR3 and CR4, respectively, colour-coded). The side chains of Met348 (carbons in orange) and the its mutation to threonine (carbon atoms in green) are shown superimposed. Key residues for this CD3-CD4 orientation are shown. Addition of calcium ions is expected to stabilise a different conformation.

S10 Fig. Detailed comparison of genetic variation measures for genomic region 2 on chromosome 5 with annotated genes shown below.

S11 Fig. Detailed comparison of genetic variation measures for genomic region 3 on chromosome 16 with annotated genes shown below.

S12 Fig. Expression patterns of protocadherin epsilon group genes, cadherin family related 1, 2, and 5 (with the transcript number in brackets) in the brain of *A. polyacanthus* across various elevated CO₂ treatments (transgenerational, developmental, acute, and control as shown in Fig. S1).

S13 Fig. AlphaFold scores for Drd4 (top) and Syap1 (middle) and Cdhr5 (bottom). (left) The pLDDT scores are shown per residue, for five models (colour-coded traces). The pLDDT plot for Syap1 and Cdhr5 show the Leu199 and Met348 models, respectively. (right) The Predicted Aligned Error (PEA) plots are shown; blue indicates low positional error. For Syap1, PAE plots obtained for the Leu199 and the Pro199 sequences are shown.